

Figure 6I: PS6 Film

Figure 6I Arrows indicate lanes utilized in figure

Lane 1: NIH-1 Veh, Lane 2: NIH-1 MK-2206 (10 nM), Lane 3: NIH-1 SC-79 (6 ug/mL)

Lane 4: **16pDel M-1 Veh**, Lane 5: **16pDel M-1 SC-79 (6ug/mL)**, Lane 6: **16pDel M-1 MK-2206 (10 nM)**

Bolded text signify lanes indicated by arrows

Figure 6I: GAPDH for PS6 film

Phospha

GAPDH #

3.27.18

#1

Figure 6I Arrows indicate lanes utilized in figure

#2 ✓

Lane 1: NIH-1 Veh, Lane 2: NIH-1 MK-2206 (10 nM), Lane 3: NIH-1 SC-79 (6 ug/mL)
Lane 4: 16pDel M-1 Veh, Lane 5: 16pDel M-1 SC-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 6: 16pDel M-1 MK-2206 (10 nM)
Bolded text signify lanes indicated by arrows

#3 ✓

Figure 6I: Total S6 Film

Total S6 3.23.18

Figure 6I Arrows indicate lanes utilized in figure

Lane 1: NIH-1 Veh, Lane 2: NIH-1 MK-2206 (10 nM), Lane 3: NIH-1 SC-79 (6 ug/mL)

Lane 4: 16pDel M-1 Veh, Lane 5: 16pDel M-1 SC-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 6: 16pDel M-1 MK-2206 (10 nM)

Bolded text signify lanes indicated by arrows

Total
GAPDH

3.27.18

Figure 6I: GAPDH for Total S6 Film

#1 ✓

Figure 6I Arrows indicate lanes utilized in figure

#2 ✓

Lane 1: NIH-1 Veh, Lane 2: NIH-1 MK-2206 (10 nM), Lane 3: NIH-1 SC-79 (6 ug/mL)
Lane 4: 16pDel M-1 Veh, Lane 5: 16pDel M-1 SC-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 6: 16pDel M-1 MK-2206 (10 nM)
Bolded text signify lanes indicated by arrows

#3 ✓